

Hearing Voices

On the Anthropology, Psychology and Politics of the Unspeakable

Rebecca-Rosea Blome

Abstract

This working paper examines the experience of hearing voices at the intersection of anthropology, psychology, and transcultural psychiatry. Beginning with the Rosenhan experiment and its lasting implications for diagnostic practice, it traces how cross-cultural research, particularly the work of Luhrmann and colleagues, shows that culturally mediated cognitive frameworks significantly shape whether voice-hearing is experienced as distressing or benign. It reviews therapeutic approaches for distressed voice-hearers grounded in compassion-focused therapy, including avatar therapy as a digital dialogue-based approach, and relates these to the Hearing Voices Movement's advocacy for an experience- and person-centred, de-pathologizing approach. Drawing on McCarthy-Jones and Longden's work on trauma, shame and memory and on Byron Good's work on political subjectivity, it considers how biographical experience and political context also shape the content of distressing voices. Originally written in 2019, this working paper includes a 2026 postscript that updates the evidence base. The studies show a deepening of relational and culturally informed approaches in voice-hearing research as well as an attempt to provide further evidence-based digital care offerings for the empowerment of voice-hearers in distress. The working paper concludes that this body of research points to compassion-focused, culturally sensitive and trauma-informed digital approaches as a particularly promising direction for sustainably supporting the recovery and empowerment of voice-hearers in distress. Their development and study require interdisciplinary collaboration at the intersection of anthropology, psychology, and the practical design and delivery of mental health care.

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From 1968 to 1972 in the US eight persons with bizarre symptomatology were hospitalized in several psychiatric clinics. All of them were hearing voices saying three certain words 'empty', 'hollow', and 'thud', but nothing else. No person other than themselves could perceive these voices. Apart from hearing these three words, none of them showed signs of a psychiatric disorder. Based on hearing three words out of any context, seven were given the diagnosis of schizophrenia in remission and for the time being, were forced to stay in the clinic. As was revealed later, all of these strange patients were mentally perfectly healthy friends of Harvard psychologist David Rosenhan, taking part in his study, which is known today as Rosenhan experiment or Thud experiment. The experiment was the onset of a profound debate about

psychiatric diagnostic practice. Until recently within psychiatry, hearing voices¹ was seen as an indisputable indicator for a present psychiatric disorder. Once uttered in the presence of a mental health professional, it usually inevitably caused psychiatric-pharmaceutical treatment and often further coercive measures like compulsory hospitalization and the like (BMBF 2010).² Currently schizophrenia is the main prevailing diagnosis for voice-hearers, but bipolar disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, and borderline personality disorder are considered as differential diagnoses (Larøi 2012).

Today it is known that also a minority of healthy people hears voices and slowly, within mental health research, there is a change starting to take place regarding the approaching of voice-hearers. Newer findings support the argument of voice-hearer activists that voice-hearing is not per se a pathological sign, but a common experience in the spectrum of the human mind, which is pre-dispositioned in everybody, but activated in relation to certain triggers³. Furthermore, in many ‘non-western’ cultures the experience of voice-hearing is seen to be normal (Beavan et al. 2011, Larøi 2012 and Corstens et al. 2014). There is evidence that not the voices people hear are problematic. ‘Cultural invitations’ provide culturally diverging ‘variations in ways of thinking about minds, persons, spirits’⁴ (Luhmann et al. 2015, 2019). This culturally mediated cognitive bias seems to have a profound impact on whether the voices are causing mental distress, or whether they might be perceived as neutral or supportive (Larøi 2012). The fear of not being able ‘to control or manage’ the voices can cause suffering and be disabling to people (Suri 2011). Luhmann and colleagues (2015, 2019) state that North American voice-hearers, who are framing their experience as psychopathological and in medical terms as e.g. ‘hallucinations’, which are part of a

¹Hearing voices is referring to the individual perceiving of auditory information in form of speech, which outsiders cannot hear. In psychiatric language the term auditory verbal hallucinations (AVH) often is used to describe the experience of hearing voices, but many voice-hearers don’t identify with that expression, which appears reducing to voice-hearer activists. Activists designate themselves as persons who hear voices or voice-hearers (Woods 2013). See page three for more information on this topic.

²The debate resulted in more precise and explicit symptom-based checklists for psychiatric disorders, listed in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM). Psychiatric practice globally builds upon the DSM, by which pathological and normative behaviours are standardized, universalized and framed in neurobiological language (BMBF 2010, Davies 2017, Kirmayer 2015).

³About 30 years after the ‘Thud-debate’, Luhmann (2001) found that US psychiatrists often relied on intuition rather than evidence-based criteria catalogues when diagnosing. Very often one or two key indicator symptoms were enough for a psychiatrist (who has little time on a single patient) to come up with a common diagnosis like schizophrenia. There is also evidence for a correlation between the development of a new class of medication for a certain spectrum of disorders and upscaling rates of diagnoses for these disorders, which are targeted by the newly developed psychopharmaceuticals (Luhmann 2001). A contemporary experiment inspired by the Thud experiment showed that in the US today within psychiatric practice, the uttering of perceiving a certain word out of context, which no one else can hear, leads to more variation in received diagnoses and prescribed psychopharmaceuticals than in the 1970s. This experiment’s voice-hearer was not in distress and able to care for her child, but received a wide variety of medication and diagnoses (BMBF 2010).

⁴They term the behind process of culturally guided direction of attention ‘social kindling’.

brain disorder, are describing their voices as severely negative. In contrast, voice-hearers from other regions, who do not have an individualized neurobiological understanding of their voices as representing aspects of a brain disorder, describe profoundly less threatening voices and sometimes report being approached in a supportive manner by the voices. Compared to ‘westerners’ from more individualistic societies, these less-suffering voice-hearers are often more likely to understand their voices and the self in relation to other people or to spirits. The more recent work by Luhrmann and colleagues is including fieldwork with ‘those for whom hallucinations are culturally valuable—who expect or even yearn to see spirits or hear god’ (Luhrmann et al. 2019: 25). One third of their non-clinical Christian interlocutors reported at least one experience of hearing god’s voice commenting in a helpful and supportive way. A similarly positive quality of the voices’ spoken content is reported by people exercising special training to enhance their ability to hear religious voices.

To empower voice-hearers in distress to actively and self-consciously determine the relations, which they have with their voices, several new therapeutic models were developed on the ground of Paul Gilbert’s compassion-focused therapy. Avatar therapy is a new therapeutic alternative, which is targeting at consciously establishing a dialogue with the voices and thereby enabling the patient to gain control of the interaction patterns. The different characters of the voices become explicitly formulated digital avatars so that through the virtual interaction, the voices can be integrated in a meaningful and peaceful way (Craig 2018). Drawing on the treatment success of compassion centred and applied dialogue therapies for voice-hearers and the research with healthy and non-clinical voice-hearers, one could conclude that culture holds coping options for distressing voice-hearing experiences and is a therapeutic and individual resource in contact with distressing voices, but at the same time, that culture can represent a potential burden for recovery and wellbeing, as is indicated by the North American example.

The Hearing Voices Movement is the internationally acting umbrella organization of activist groups from all over the world, supporting the needs and rights of people who are hearing voices and are likely to identify themselves as voice-hearers.⁵

The voice-bearer (i) asserts voice-hearing as a meaningful experience, (ii) challenges psychiatric authority and (iii) builds identity through sharing life narrative. (Woods 2013)

The Hearing Voices Movement favours an experience or person-centred approach to voice-hearing, including subjectivities and seeing mental distress or seemingly

⁵By the activists’ engagement for a change in the psychiatric and common approaching of persons who hear voices and their questioning of a disease centred approach to voice-hearing – (self-determined) ‘voice-hearer’ is a ‘politically resonant and value-laden identity’. (...) The figure of “the voice-hearer” comes into being through a specific set of narrative practices as an “expert by experience” who challenges the authority and diagnostic categories of mainstream psychiatry, especially the category of “schizophrenia.” (Woods 2013).

extraordinary mental experiences as meaningful experiences. They engage for a general shift in perception of hearing voices as ‘common experience’⁶, possibly linked to something painful or emotionally overwhelming in the past. Voices are seen to potentially provide hints to aspects of one’s inner world, that should be actively considered by the voice-hearer, but are not yet. They suggest to start asking ‘What has happened to you?’ rather than ‘What is wrong with you?’ (as usually is the case within mental health care).⁷ Much psychological research on voice-hearing highlights previous traumatic experiences as ‘risk factors’ for hearing distressing voices⁸. Many suffering voice-hearers report voices appearing in the shape of the voices of their former perpetrators or the voices’ spoken content is reviving traumatic experiences. Thereby trauma is not exclusively to be understood as a single traumatic event, like for example the often-associated experience of rape, but also as repetitive experiences of perverted patterns of people’s behaviour as e.g. long-term emotional abuse by care-givers and a wide range of other emotionally overwhelming situations (McCarthy-Jones and Longden 2015, Longden 2017, Luhrmann et al. 2019). One psychological scheme of explanation for a triggering of voice-hearing by previous traumatic experiences leading to mental distress focusses on the shaping of memories by the current cognitive and emotional state of the voice-hearer.⁹ McCarthy-Jones and Longden (2015) identify shame and guilt as emotions commonly linked to current perceptions and memories of the trauma associated by voice-hearers — thereby re-shaping the memory representation of the trauma, which then appears, re-loaded with these emotions, in the form of the voices’ spoken distressing content.¹⁰

Trauma and psychosis are at times inextricably linked to what is ‘unspoken, unsaid, repressed and unspeakable’ (Good 2012). Thinking on trauma from a political

⁶One leading figure here is Eleanor Longden. She is a PhD psychologist, voice-hearer and voice-hearing activist, who made the topic more popular by a TED talk, which has now been watched more than four million times (Longden 2013).

⁷Hearing Voices Movement (2013)

⁸Luhrmann et al. (2019) show that ‘trauma increases risk for hallucinations and psychosis’, but is just one of multiple pathways to distressing voice-hearing.

⁹The explanation draws on a psychological view of memories as ‘transitory dynamic mental construction(s)’ (...) ‘which are constructed in the present moment according to the needs of the present moment’ (Conway and Pleydell-Pearce 2000 and Fernyhough 2012 in McCarthy-Jones and Longden 2015).

¹⁰Further regarding experiences of trauma as underlying causes for voice-hearing: the phenomenologies and aetiologies are similar for people who are DSM-based diagnosed with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and voice-hearers with schizophrenia. Thereby the authors are questioning the differentiation of ‘voice-hearer disorders’ into dissociative and psychotic voice-hearers, since the experiences seem to be very much the same. Instead they suggest focussing on the development of a common trans-diagnostic treatment strategy, thereby addressing the underlying causes for developing mentally distressing voice-hearing experiences and focussing on supporting the wellbeing of voice-hearers (McCarthy-Jones and Longden 2015).

subjectivity perspective¹¹, as one of multiple pathways to hearing voices, again sheds a different light on voice-hearing¹².

I am suggesting in general that in anthropological research we need to listen to what is unspoken, unsaid, repressed and unspeakable—in politics and in everyday life as well as in psychopathology—and to attend our own resistance to knowing as much as to the complex forms of resistance to knowing of those with whom we work.
(Good 2012)

Regarding (post-)conflict settings, hearing voices might sometimes be a mechanism of survivors of political violence to cope with emotionally overwhelming experience(s) that had to be repressed—be it due to political reasons or due to social taboo surrounding the traumatic experience(s), as is usually the case in relation to (sexualized) political violence. Collective experiences of terror of such kind might in a hidden manner even become integrated into the collective memory. In the extreme but relevant example of politically motivated sexualized violence, cultural coding in most cases identifies the topic as illegitimate for entering the public sphere. Thus these painful experiences will never become integrated into the historical narrative, nor the individual (official) narrative, and through the taboo of articulation and the fear of stigma and shame—leading to silence.¹³

When understood as intense affective experience for which there are no words, or which is unspeakable due to political repression or cultural taboo — hearing voices can be seen as an outcome of (politically) forced forgetting or silencing, and thus as at times potentially constituting a form of psychological resistance by affected minds¹⁴ towards this silencing. The following excursion into hauntology and hearing voices is exemplifying the political and cultural load of the unspoken that voice-hearers might silently carry along with themselves. Byron Good (2012) brings an example from a young man with psychosis from Java, who is experiencing the hearing of voices and being haunted by bad spirits. It turns out that his story was interwoven with a local history of political violence covered by silence, including the circumstances of the politically related death of his father. As explicitly expressed by themselves, the anthropologists were only able to understand the case, when linking the psychological

¹¹Inspired by works of João Biehl and Byron Good, by political subjectivity I mean inner processes of the affected political subject, including affected states and agency understood in relation to power hierarchies, which are analysable under aspects of marginalization, political oppression, coloniality, violence and gender.

¹²As the similarities in phenomenologies of suffering and non-suffering voice-hearers do as well.

¹³'Women don't speak' was an important insight of the first Transitional Justice trials held in Peru and South Africa, where none of the survivors of sexualized violence were speaking out in public about their experience in these peace and justice trials.

¹⁴From an anthropological perspective silence, remembering and forgetting are always entangled strategies to cope with the past (Argenti and Schramm 2010). Remembering thereby is selective and situated, and a collective process of self-representation, rather than an individual one (Terdiman 2003, Halbmeier and Karl 2012).

to the political. By this case the author shows the ‘relevance to the issues of political subjectivity and violence’ and the urge for anthropologists to think psychologically for being capable of understanding collective and individual linkages to political violence and structural inequalities, and—extending this thought on trauma and distressing voices as outcome of political violence—also to think politically to understand the psychological.

If hearing voices at times might be a coping strategy of affected minds¹⁵—balancing traumatizing experiences—hearing voices might sometimes also be a form of psychological resistance to political oppression.¹⁶ Without the need to question medical help and psychiatric diagnostics for people in mental distress per se, since not the voices themselves are problematic, but what people think of them— therapeutic approaches seem productive, which are empowering voice-hearers to determine the relationships with the voices by themselves. Particularly with regard to guilt and shame as the trauma-memory accompanying and possibly triggering emotions in the onset of distressing voice-hearing experiences, a removal of stigmatizing and a de-pathologizing of hearing voices within mental health and public discourses might be helpful to support a meaningful and peaceful integration of the voices’ references. This is where anthropology and psychiatry should collaborate and by including a political subjectivity approach, linking thoughts on structural inequality, violence, discourses on stigma and marginalization and knowledge on cultural codes for the unspeakable and the speakable with psychiatric practice. Interdisciplinary approaches hold the potential to contribute to the integrating of the unspeakable as a possible form of psychological resistance to politically silenced truths and thereby supporting the recovery and wellbeing of survivors of political violence.

¹⁵Current dominant psychiatric practice might often lead to medicalizing and pathologizing these normal answers to painful experiences and in turn to the stigmatization of survivors of difficult or violent experiences (McCarthy-Jones and Longden 2015, Longden 2017, Hearing Voices Movement 2013).

¹⁶In this context voices are usually distressing and often can be a sign of a present psychopathology. Since the voice-hearers’ mental distress here emerges by understandable coping mechanisms and not due to a physiological brain disorder, the question remains if medication targeting at transforming neurobiological processes should remain a major way to approach survivors of violence with this symptomatology. Particularly since cognitive bias and current emotional states are shaping the voice-hearing experience, cultural treatment resources could be approached as well. Considering the role of taboo and political oppression in relation to trauma and furthermore the danger that the stigma which is surrounding disorder diagnoses could be additionally adding up to the stigma which is at times associated with the trauma itself — trans-diagnostic treatment strategy alternatives (McCarthy-Jones and Longden 2015) seem necessary. Approaches focussing on compassion appear worthy to be further explored in this context, since they could support the wellbeing of this type of traumatized distressed voice-hearers by enabling the integration of repressed or painful and shameful memories and thereby empower distressed voice-hearers in a ‘sustainable’ manner to change their condition for the better.

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POSTSCRIPT (2026)

Since this working paper was written in 2019, several developments have advanced the research landscape it describes. The most significant concerns avatar therapy. The single-site trial cited in this working paper (Craig et al. 2018) has since been followed by AVATAR2, a Phase 2/3 multi-centre randomised controlled trial with 345 participants across four study sites in the United Kingdom, published in *Nature Medicine* (Ward et al. 2024). Both a brief and an extended version of avatar therapy significantly reduced voice-related distress at 16 weeks compared to treatment as usual, with the extended version meeting the threshold for clinically significant change. However, these effects were no longer statistically significant at 28 weeks, leaving the question of long-term sustainability open. The authors describe avatar therapy as part of “a wave of relational approaches, informed by advances in theory, which position voice-hearing as an experience of social communication” (Ward et al. 2024). The aim of the therapy is to reduce voice-related distress and build empowerment in daily life through facilitated dialogues between the voice-hearer and a digital embodiment of the distressing voice, supported by a therapist. AVATAR2 marks a milestone in digital, compassion-oriented dialogical care for voice-hearers in need of support.

Luhrmann's long-running interdisciplinary research on voice-hearing at the intersection of anthropology and transcultural psychiatry, which formed a central reference in this working paper, has been substantially extended. Luhrmann et al. (2023) compared communities in which voice-hearing is common and expected, including Christian charismatics, mediums and tulpamancers, and found that all utilise cultural models to identify and explain voice-like events, with shared practices of "discernment." Ng, Chen, Zhao and Luhrmann (2025) extended the comparison to Shanghai, China, finding that voices reported by participants there were notably more concerned with politics, more relational in quality and characterised by benevolent persuasion rather than harsh command. Altman et al. (2025) reported culturally specific voice content among Russian participants diagnosed with schizophrenia in Kazan, where commands tended to be non-violent and focused on activities associated with daily life. Together, these studies further support the social kindling hypothesis of Luhrmann and colleagues, as discussed in the original working paper for US, Indian and Ghanaian voice-hearers, now across additional cultural settings.

Beyond avatar therapy, further digital tools for distressed voice-hearers have begun to be developed and tested. A smartphone app called Temstem, developed with and for clinical voice-hearers, showed momentary reductions in voice-hearing distress within sessions (Jongeneel et al. 2022). However, a subsequent randomised controlled trial with 89 outpatients suffering from frequent distressing voices found that unguided use of Temstem did not significantly reduce voice-hearing distress or improve social functioning in daily life (Jongeneel et al. 2024). The authors conclude that therapeutic guidance may be necessary to optimise effectiveness, noting that meta-analyses have shown guided digital mental health interventions to be significantly more effective than unguided ones (Baumeister et al. 2014 and Karyotaki et al. 2021, cited in Jongeneel et al. 2024). How digital tools for distressed voice-hearers can be designed to support meaningful relational engagement with voices, rather than symptom management alone, remains an open question.

The studies discussed here show a deepening of relational and culturally informed approaches in voice-hearing research since 2019, as well as an attempt to provide evidence-based digital care offerings for the empowerment of voice-hearers in distress. Building on the reflections of this working paper, further compassion-focused, trauma-sensitive digital care approaches that take into account both the cultural codes and the biographical circumstances shaping experiences of voice-hearing may hold particular promise for sustainable success. Their development would warrant further interdisciplinary research at the intersection of anthropology, psychology, and the practical design and delivery of mental health care.

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